

FUTURELAKES

For Nature, Climate and People

Catalogue of citizen science schemes

Milestone 3

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Summary

This document aims to introduce project participants to Citizen Science (CS) and to assist them with selection of CSi activities, based on certain criteria, which are relevant to lakes and that support the Mission Ocean & Waters goals. We first explain the meaning, importance and usefulness of the CS concept in lakes and then provide the methodology used to create a catalogue of existing CS schemes, and the data post processing. We conclude with some suggested schemes for each Mission aim. This is meant to give the readers a good understanding of the catalogue and of the proposed guidelines for detailing, selecting and designing CS schemes depending on general parameters and local contexts (i.e., availability of resources and volunteers' maturity level).

Disclaimer

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1 Introduction

Citizen science (CS) has emerged as a transformative approach in environmental research, offering scientific, technological, and societal benefits while democratising knowledge production. Citizen science offers an effective way to actively involve the public, fostering greater ownership, empowerment, and ultimately, collaborative lake governance. It actively involves local communities in research and monitoring efforts, generates valuable data, promotes environmental stewardship, and supports informed and inclusive decision-making.

The added value of CS is multifaceted as volunteers can collect data across large areas with high frequency (EC 2018), the resulting data can have high value if standardized protocols are used or if expert validation is applied (PPSR 2022) and as a result, the process can alert local authorities of environmental concerns, for example if harmful algal blooms or pollution events occur or invasive species are recorded (IPBES 2019). The importance is highlighted by the fact that since 2021 the European Commission Joint Research Centre (JRC) hosts its own CS “Data Collection Hub”. The technological development has come to the aid of CS-created data robustness as Machine Learning can be applied to clean (or fill) the data (IUCN, 2020) or even introduce blockchains for transparency (EC 2025). Besides the technical benefits, CS can foster public awareness, environmental education, policy influence and inclusive governance (IPBES 2019). The practice of CS aligns with FAIR principles, reduces knowledge monopolies and empowers marginalised group either by engaging underrepresented communities or by enabling citizens to co-develop restoration strategies (EC 2023)

There are numerous ways for volunteers to engage in scientific activities, reflecting the wide diversity of citizen science approaches. However, this variety can be difficult to navigate for those looking to organize a citizen science project, and it is important to recognize that citizen science is not always the most suitable or effective method for every research or monitoring need (Pocock et al. 2014).

1.1 Purpose of a Citizen Science Catalogue

CS is a fundamental aspect in the FutureLakes project, supporting community engagement and transformative change (along with awareness-raising) and data generation related to lake restoration and monitoring programmes. This Milestone report accompanies a catalogue of relevant citizen science schemes for lake communities to support Demo Basin partners in their working with communities. The catalogue and report supports the FutureLakes objective for each Demo site to identify and establish at least one citizen science activity (M) in their basin that provides data of relevance to local users and policy needs. Citizen science is a fundamental tool for FutureLakes to illustrate how it can help in developing an engaged and mobilized citizenry at all 6 Demo Basins, while simultaneously strengthening policy integration, increase public trust, ensure inclusivity and broaden representation. CS will ultimately support FutureLakes Pillars (Innovation, Circularity and Biodiversity) to provide the foundation for planned solutions (NBS, CBS, BfS) to tackle nutrient pollution, habitat degradation, legacy nutrients in lake sediments and the recovery and reuse of biomass and sediments

Having set the “when” in the Grant Agreement (giving enough time to deploy CS schemes for more than a year in all Demo Basins), this report assists how to involve citizens.

How FutureLakes understands the engagement: an open procedure, supported, mediated, organised after having conducted targeted workshops (with different key actors to depict the vision, locate the barriers and pinpoint the needs) and media campaigns.

Step 1: Conceptual Basis – Why Engage Citizens in Lake Restoration?

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Engaging citizens in European lake restoration serves multiple interconnected targets: filling critical data gaps (e.g., pollution hotspots, biodiversity trends), raising awareness, and fostering bottom-up pressure for policy change. The "why" hinges on integrating diverse knowledge types—not just scientific data but also local empirical knowledge (e.g., fishers' observations) and Traditional Ecological Knowledge (e.g., historical land-use practices)—to create a holistic evidence base. This aligns with EU priorities like the Biodiversity Strategy 2030 and Water Framework Directive, where citizen input can pinpoint pollution sources, advocate for blue-green economy transitions, and monitor restoration efficacy. Crucially, participation transforms passive stakeholders into active stewards, bridging gaps between science, policy, and community needs.

Step 2: Implementation – Tailored Approaches per Demo Basin

Implementation requires site-specific strategies tailored to cultural readiness, existing stewardship networks, and technical capacity. Mapping Stakeholders directly replies to the question of WHOM to engage: Identify local NGOs, schools, and fishermen/anglers who can co-design activities or just participate in tailored activities. Activities (WHAT): All sort of combinations starting from water quality sampling (using low-cost kits), photographic observations, anglers' logs up to oral history interviews to document ecological changes may apply depending on the aims set during step 1 and the local community maturity and needs. Methods (HOW): Deploy scalable tools like the ones presented below for data consistency, while adapting engagement methods (e.g., gamification for youth, workshops for elders).

The JRC's citizen science guidelines and ECSA's principles ensure rigor, while demo basins act as living labs to test interdisciplinary frameworks—balancing technical precision with social inclusivity. Good understanding of technical issues can lead to selection of best scheme per demo site (depending on volunteers' cultural, preparedness, and awareness levels, existing stewardship schemes, combined also with a range of ecological and social parameters. To this point, using D2.1 (mapping) and the workshops within T2.4, the Demo Basin leads (and/or groups) will consult the catalogue (M3) to select the optimal CS scheme(s) tailored to their Demo Basing and restoration plans.

1.2 Methodology

The purpose of this report was to review established citizen science programs that focus on lakes and align with the three pillars of Mission Ocean & Waters: reducing pollution, restoring biodiversity, and enhancing the blue economy. Additionally, a fourth criterion of sustainability was considered, which depends on the engagement of local communities in the Demo Basin.

The methodology applied can be divided into five main steps: review procedure, generation of descriptors, organization of the database, and designing selection criteria to assist the Demo Basin teams.

1.2.1 Review Procedure

The review procedure involved conducting a scoping review of recent EU publications, including those from Horizon projects and citizen science associations. The goal was to investigate the range and nature of existing literature that supports both qualitative and quantitative criteria. This process aimed to create a list of potential information sources (hyperlinks), including grey literature.

In particular, three scientific repositories - Science Direct, Scopus, and Web of Science - along with Google Scholar, were utilized as search tools to ensure comprehensive coverage across a wide range of scientific disciplines, including citizen science studies. Additionally, citizen science platforms were

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evaluated, encompassing various initiatives as well as lake-specific schemes. The assessed open-data repositories consist of national and global citizen science platforms and provide information about specific projects or scientific topics, as well as academic and scientific platforms that encompass citizen science issues. Table 1 presents an overview of the most established citizen science platforms utilized in this study, while Table 2 provides an overview of noteworthy citizen science-related organizations.

The scientific repositories were searched by using various combinations of the keyword “Lake” with the following terms: “citizen science”, “participatory/public participation”, “community-based”, “crowdsourcing”, “volunteer”, “biodiversity”, “water quality”, “pollution”, “(blue/green/circular) economy”. The search was conducted solely in English, with no restrictions on time or origin, employing a non-exclusive procedure to accommodate emerging sources. Alongside, the citizen science platforms and inventories were searched based on the provided filters, including “Keywords”, “Field of science”, “Name of project”, “Type of Hub”, “Country”, and “Geographic extent”.

The aforementioned procedure led to an initial collection of potential citizen science publications and projects related to lakes, identified from February to June 2025, that were subsequently selected for full-text evaluation.

Table 1 Citizen science platforms and inventories (modified after Wehn et al 2024).

Name	Webpage	Description
Wavelinks	https://wavelinks.inventory	A Mission Ocean Citizen Science inventory
EU-citizen.science	https://eu-citizen.science/	A European Union Citizen Science online platform
iNaturalist	https://www.inaturalist.org/	An online platform of people sharing biodiversity
MICS platform	https://mics.tools/	A citizen science impact assessment platform
Project Noah	https://www.projectnoah.org/	A community-powered digital catalog of species
SciStarter	https://scistarter.org/	Global citizen science platform
Zooniverse	https://www.zooniverse.org/	Platform for people-powered research
CitSci	https:// Citsci.org	Global citizen science support platform
CitizenScience.gov	https:// CitizenScience.gov	Platform for citizen science across the U.S. government
GEO AquaWatch	www.geoaquawatch.org	Water quality database inventory
JRC Data Catalogue	https://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/datas et/jrc-citsci-10004	Environmental policies inventory

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Table 2 Citizen science-related organizations.

Source	Webpage	Description
Australian Citizen Science Association (ACSA)	https://biocollect.ala.org.au/	A member-based incorporated association that seeks to advance citizen science.
Citizen Science Association (CSA)	https://citizenscience.org/	A member-driven organization dedicated to advancing citizen science.
Earthwatch	https://earthwatch.org.uk/	An international environmental NGO that actively engages the public in scientific research through citizen science projects.
European Citizen Science Association (ECSA)	https://ecsa.citizen-science.net/	A non-profit membership organization to promote citizen science in Europe.

It is important to elaborate here on the contributions of the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA). ECSA has played a crucial role in professionalizing citizen science, ensuring that it is recognized as a legitimate research methodology, policy tool, and method of public engagement. By establishing standards through ten key principles, fostering collaboration via various EU-funded projects, and launching the EU-Citizen Science platform, ECSA has made significant strides in this area. The association provides guidelines on data quality, legal considerations, and participatory methods, facilitating collaboration between researchers and citizen communities. Furthermore, ECSA has influenced EU policies and contributed to the EU Citizen Science Strategy 2020. Overall, ECSA has greatly expanded the reach and impact of citizen science across Europe, promoting it through observatories and connections with public health initiatives that address societal challenges.

Following that, a full-text review was conducted, which included a screening and eligibility process to narrow down the list of potential lake-related citizen science publications to those specifically focused on lakes. This was achieved by applying a set of inclusion and exclusion criteria, as detailed in the table below. The selected criteria were established to ensure maximum scientific transparency and reliability of the results.

Table 3 Inclusion/exclusion criteria developed for the screening and eligibility process.

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Include schemes that involve at least one lake water body, even if the operation scale is very limited. – Include schemes that primarily focus on various water bodies, ensuring to mention at least one lake in the results. – Include schemes that reference the study of general categories of water bodies, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Exclude schemes that were mentioned on a database but haven't provided any observations or records since their development (no public participation). – Exclude any schemes listed in a database that do not have external links for additional information.

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<p>such as freshwater and surface waters, which scientifically include lakes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Include schemes that reference the study of a specific watershed that contains lakes. - Include schemes designed to work on watershed scale, which scientifically includes lakes. - Include schemes that reference the study of a specific river basin that contains lakes. - Include schemes designed to work on river basin scale, which scientifically includes lakes. - Include schemes that mention to study wetlands, but include lakes as type of wetland (Australian wetlands). - Include schemes that focus on animals and plants inhabiting lakes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exclude schemes where the full text was written in a language other than English. - Exclude duplicate schemes (registered in more than one database). - Exclude schemes that do not allow open access to the full text.
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At this point, the review process has concluded, followed by the generation of the descriptors as described in the next section.

1.2.2 Descriptors

An essential part of the methodology involves selecting descriptors that aid in the segmentation and optimal organization of the collected information. Key factors to consider when choosing descriptors include how they are formulated and the type of data they provide.

In particular, the selection of descriptors was tailored to meet the report's needs and objectives, addressing the questions: 'What information should the database provide?' and 'What purpose does it aim to achieve?'. Therefore, an initial set of descriptors was generated to address the two main questions and identify the essential information that needs to be tracked.

Subsequently, the formulation of these descriptors was determined by examining how descriptors from existing acknowledged citizen science inventories were structured. All the citizen science inventories used for comparison were obtained from the publications included in the scoping review. This approach ensures that the resulting database will be a recognizable and comparable inventory that conforms to international and European standards.

Finally, the appropriate type of data (such as text, numbers, dates, 'yes'/'no' responses, etc.) was selected for each descriptor. Each selection was made to ensure data consistency and to simplify the process of storing the information and analysing the results.

1.2.3 Database organisation

Database organization refers to the overall way the database is structured and includes all the necessary actions that ensure accurate reading and easy use of the selected information. In particular, this step focused on determining the best order for presenting the descriptors to ensure data consistency. When deciding on the order, it's important to consider the significance and content of the information each descriptor provides. For instance, descriptors that offer basic but fundamental

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information of general interest about a citizen science scheme were placed at the beginning of the database (e.g. short description of the scheme), while those that contain more specialized, expert-level information were positioned at the end (e.g. social network approaches).

Furthermore, the database organization incorporated filters to enhance post-processing analysis. This functionality aimed to simplify and expedite navigation within the database by applying filters to sort and display the desired information based on selected criteria. For example, by adjusting the filter on the “Name of the scheme” descriptor, the information can be sorted in ascending order. Additionally, by applying selected criteria of the filter on the “Field of science” descriptor, only Water Science-related schemes can be displayed.

1.2.4 Selection criteria

The main idea of this section was to develop several criteria that could be used to outline the citizen science schemes in the database by providing information in a more targeted manner through the use of specific descriptors. In particular, the selected criteria were intended to provide insights into several key aspects of the retrieved citizen science schemes, such as the connection between citizen science initiatives in lakes and the three key areas of the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters" (protecting biodiversity, stopping pollution, and enhancing the blue economy), the feasibility of documenting data collected by citizens, the practicality of implementing citizen science projects of a specific scientific purpose and focus area, and the main challenges that may arise, as well as the maturity of volunteer groups to participate in projects that prioritize social benefits rather than personal gain. The information required to describe the aforementioned aspects can be provided by the descriptors within the developed database. Therefore, the criteria were established alongside these descriptors, which have already defined the information available for the reviewed citizen science initiatives.

This process resulted in the selection of seven criteria, which are formulated as follows:

1. Relevance to one or more Mission Ocean pillars
2. Robustness of citizen-generated data for policy uptake
3. Engagement-related aspects
4. Investment in Cost and time versus benefits
5. Complexity of protocols
6. Openness & Accessibility of data
7. Scaling up – Barriers

The seven criteria were developed to thoroughly describe the essential aspects of the citizen science schemes that were reviewed and to ensure a clear connection to the descriptors by grouping multiple descriptors under each criterion. The seven criteria were then used to create mini CiSciBoxes for each of the evaluated citizen science schemes, based on the relevant information from the corresponding descriptors. More details about the connection and grouping of the descriptors, and examples of mini CiSciBoxes with the selected criteria, are provided in the results section. ^[10]

2 Findings

2.1 Scoping review and descriptors

The review process led to the creation of a primary database that includes about 170 schemes focused specifically on lake-related initiatives. This database is the main outcome of the report. Most of the schemes were sourced from citizen science platforms, with the JRC inventory featuring over 300 citizen science projects across various scientific fields that required review. Additionally, the scoping review of scientific repositories yielded 60 publications in total, including both articles and reviews. Most of these articles studied the results of citizen science schemes that were part of larger projects or programs, while the majority of the projects and programs were citizen science initiatives funded or partly supported by the EU, national, and governmental organizations.

Additionally, a secondary database was established that includes more than 100 citizen science projects activated during the initial search, which do not specifically target lakes. This resulted from compiling publications that contain the keyword “lake” as a general reference, rather than as a specific case study. Moreover, projects from citizen science platforms that were initially included based on broad searching categories, such as “Field of Science: Ocean, Water, and Marine” ended up being ocean and/or marine-related. The secondary database was separated and treated as an extra source of information that could be of potential use for basin management.

The descriptors generation process resulted in a total of 43 descriptors that were organized into five major groups (Figure 1), as follows:

Group A - Basic information: this group contained general information like i) full name, ii) abbreviation, iii) brief description, iv) the program’s scope/objectives, v) if it was launched as a mobile app or a web app, vi) the link to its source for more details or a download, vii) the creator (the organization) and the host, viii) the developer, and ix) the origin (initial location) of the CS scheme.

Group B – Participation and engagement methodology: in this group, mostly functional indicators were included related to the design, engagement type and social science models like i) citizen science approaches, meaning if the CS scheme is targeting lake-based community action projects - for local communities, or educational/captive research learning projects - for schools, employees, museums, etc., or Interest-group investigation projects - for citizens with prior knowledge/expertise/interest in the topic and even Mass-participation census projects - for the general public, ii) the degree of volunteer involvement, meaning crowdsourcing or distributed intelligence, or participatory science up to extreme citizen science, iii) the type of projects if they are/were contributory, collaborative or co-created ones, iv) the time scale of the proposed methods (particular months, seasons, or all year long), v) the frequency of the proposed methods (regular or occasional), vi) the social networking approaches (e.g. meeting, workshops, social media campaigns, educational/training sessions, platforms among others), vii) the social uptake assessed in three-scales (limited, considerable and large), and viii) the stakeholders (e.g. governments, associations, institutions, NGOs, the general public).

Group C – Fields of operation: in this group, mostly operational indicators were included related to the function, field of science, scale of operation and operational goals like i) the App functionality, meaning if the CS scheme is providing a mobile app and if yes, what functionalities it includes: surveys, spotting, sensing, image and video classification, gamification, ii) the Web functionality, meaning if the CS scheme is providing a Web app and if yes, what functionalities it includes: present active citizen science projects and activities, display citizen science data and information, provide overall guidelines and tools that can be used to support citizen science projects and activities in general, present good practice examples and lessons learned, offer relevant scientific outcomes for people who are involved or interested in citizen science, gamification iii) the field of science (e.g. water science, natural science, environmental science), iv) the scale of operation (local, regional, national, global), v) the relevant

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Sustainable Development Goals (e.g. SDG 1, SDG 2), vi) the goals of the EU Ocean Mission, which are the protecting biodiversity, stopping pollution and enhancing blue economy, vii) the study site, in case the scheme is incorporated a specific study site, viii) the types of water bodies (e.g. lakes, rivers, marine, ocean), and ix) the policy aims, meaning the desired outcomes that a CS scheme seeks to achieve.

Group D – Technology and application: in this group, mostly technological indicators were included related to technological characteristics and application processes like i) whether the CS scheme is included in a CS platform, and if yes ii) what type of CS platform is, meaning if the CS platform is a commercial platform, a platform for specific projects, a platform for specific scientific topics, a national platform, an EU platform or an academic/scientific platform, iii) the demand for constant internet connection, iv) the technological methods applied (e.g. water sampling kits and instruments), v) the reporting device, meaning the method used to report measurements (surveys, via app or web), vi) the requirement for volunteer training (yes or no), and vii) the provision of expert validation (yes or no).

Group E – Accessibility: in this group, mostly accessibility indicators were included related to physical, digital, and social access like i) the number of records, ii) the openness of data, meaning the free access to all data, iii) if the scheme is still active (yes or no), iv) the start date (year), and v) the end date (year).

Basic information	Participation & Engagement Methodology	Fields of operation	Technology & Applications	Accessibility
Full name	Citizen science approaches	App functionality	Type of CS platform	# Records
Abbreviation	Degree of involvement of volunteers	Web functionality	Platform/Website	Open-access data
Brief description	Types of projects	Field of science	Tech methods	Still active
Program objectives	Time scale (daily, monthly, seasonally, annually, all year)	Scale of operation (local, regional, national, global)	What to measure	Start date
Mobile App or Web	Frequency (once, regularly, occasionally)	Relevant Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)	Constant internet connection	End date
Link	Social networking approaches	Goal of the EU Ocean Mission	Volunteer training	
Host/Larger org	Social uptake	Study site	Expert validation	
Developer	Stakeholders	Water body		
Origin		Policy aims		

Figure 1 Classification of the selected descriptors into five main groups.

2.2 Post processing analysis

Post-processing analysis of the collected information enhanced the graphic depiction of key points of interest, leading to considerable conclusions. In particular, the distribution percentages of lake-specific citizen science schemes worldwide (Figure 2) highlighted the trend of employing citizen science approaches across various countries, with the USA and Europe leading the way. The graphical representation of distribution percentages was created using the "Origin" descriptor, which indicates the original location of the scheme's conception.

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Figure 2 Percentage distribution of the “Origin” descriptor.

It is important to note that since the English language was established as a limiting criterion, it was anticipated that most of the citizen science schemes retrieved during the scoping review would originate from English-speaking countries, such as the United States, European nations, Canada, and Australia. Citizen science is inherently focused on activities that involve general public in scientific research. Therefore, it is understandable that projects developed in countries where English is not the common language should be created in local (native) languages to address their citizens and local communities. As a result, contributions from countries in Asia and Africa are likely to be underrepresented.

While Figure 2 shows the spatial distribution of citizen science schemes based on the country of origin, Figure 3 illustrates the scale of operation. Many projects are inspired to address the needs of a particular study area (local scale). Some projects have been tested on pilot areas as part of research, but aim for broader recognition and usage (regional, national, and multinational scale). It is true that most CS schemes are designed in English language so these countries get to be more represented in Figure 2, but are more In several occasions where some of the apps were originally designed or translated in several languages (i.e. Aquality app runs in 6 languages, Litterati in 12, BloomWatch in 39, and FreshWaterWatch along with EPA Sanitary Survey App for Marine and Fresh Waters hold the record with 42 languages). Furthermore, there are projects designed to be adaptable anywhere, without boundary limitations (global scale). As a result, the original location of the scheme’s conception is not the sole determinant of a project’s application scale.

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Figure 3 Percentage distribution of the scale of operation.

Additionally, the analysis indicated that initiatives involving lake-related citizen science are primarily focused on lakes, ponds, and reservoirs, while the rest of the programs include lake sites by facilitating freshwater resources or all types of water bodies (lakes, rivers, marine, ocean) in general (Figure 4). The graphical representation of distribution percentages was created using the "Water body" descriptor, which refers to the various types of water bodies included in the citizen science schemes of the created database.

Figure 4 Percentage distribution of the "Water body" descriptor.

Additionally, a noteworthy result related to the report's objectives is the analysis of the EU Mission's goal to "Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030." Specifically, it is essential to consider how the goals of citizen science initiatives are aligned with the three pillars of the Ocean Mission: protecting biodiversity, stopping pollution, and enhancing the blue economy. The post-analysis indicated that the primary goal of the Ocean Mission selected by the lake-related citizen science initiatives was to stop pollution. This was followed by the goal of protecting biodiversity, with the enhancement of the blue economy ranking as the least emphasized objective (Figure 5). A graphical percentage distribution was created using the "Goal of the EU Mission: Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030" descriptor, which illustrates the participation rates of the lake-related citizen science programs per Ocean Mission, as well as the combinations of these missions and the total participation across all three.

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Figure 5 Percentage distribution of the "Goal of the EU Mission: Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030" descriptor per Ocean Mission.

2.3 Linking descriptors to criteria

A key outcome of the applied methodology is the connection of the descriptors with the chosen criteria, which were designed to present the generated information of specific descriptors in a more focused manner by categorizing them into seven groups. The table below presents six of the seven selected criteria. The criterion "Relevance to one or more Mission Ocean pillars" pertains only to the descriptor "Goal of the EU Mission: Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030". Therefore, it is not included as one of the criteria in the table but is addressed under the "Scaling up – barriers" criterion.

Table 4 The 26 descriptors that formed the 6 selected criteria.

Engagement - related aspects	Protocols & Complexity	Investment in Cost & Time Vs Benefits	Openness & Accessibility data (robustness & policy uptake)	Scaling up - Barriers
Citizen Science approaches	App/Web Functionality	Constant internet connection	Type of CS platform	Study site
Types of projects	Volunteer training	Tech & Methods	Field of Science	Water body
Degree of involvement of volunteers	Expert validation	Measurements	Relevant SDGs	Scale of operation
Social networking approaches	Time scale		Access to all data	Social uptake
Stakeholders	Frequency		Mobile App or Web App	Start, end date & still active
			Number of records	Goal of the EU Mission: Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030
			Policy aims	

2.4 Guidance / Suggestions to Demo Basin

Citizen science (CS) schemes exhibit a **multiplicity of targets**, ranging from environmental monitoring and public health to social innovation and policy co-creation. Their potential for **establishment, design, and implementation** depends on factors such as funding structures, technological accessibility, and stakeholder engagement. However, challenges arise in **standardization, data quality, and long-term participation**, particularly when projects scale from local to EU-wide initiatives. The **European Citizen Science Association (ECSA)** and **OECD** emphasize embedding CS in policy frameworks to enhance

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legitimacy, while the **JRC** provides guidelines for methodological rigor. The **OECD's citizen science embedding policy** underscores the need for institutionalization, urging governments to integrate CS into national research strategies to enhance their utility. Despite these efforts, fragmented governance and inconsistent documentation hinder seamless integration into EU policy mechanisms, such as the **Green Deal** and **Horizon Europe**.

The **sustainability of CS schemes** is governed by three key pillars: **institutional support, community ownership, and financial viability**. According to **ECSA and IUCN**, projects that align with long-term policy goals (e.g., biodiversity restoration, climate adaptation) are more likely to secure sustained funding and institutional backing. Meanwhile, the **OECD** highlights the need for **formalized partnerships** between researchers, policymakers, and civil society to prevent project abandonment post-funding. Practicality often hinges on **digital infrastructure** and **participatory design**, ensuring that projects remain adaptable to community needs while meeting scientific and regulatory standards.

EU policy relevance further dictates CS sustainability, as initiatives like the **European Solidarity Corps (ESC)** and **Copernicus** demonstrate how citizen-generated data can complement official monitoring systems. In the EU, this means anchoring CS in directives like the *Open Science Charter* and ensuring cross-border collaboration via networks like **ESFRI**. Without structural reforms, CS risks remaining a niche tool rather than a transformative approach to democratizing knowledge and policymaking. However, gaps persist in **documentation and impact assessment**, with many projects lacking structured frameworks for evaluating long-term outcomes. To ensure enduring success, CS must transition from **ad-hoc volunteer efforts to institutionalized practices**, supported by **EU-wide funding streams, standardized protocols (JRC), and clear pathways for policy uptake**. Ultimately, the interplay between **grassroots engagement and top-down governance** will determine whether CS becomes a permanent fixture in Europe's scientific and democratic landscape.

Exploring catalogue

To explore potential schemes for your lake community, we recommend you first consider what Mission Ocean & Waters aims you are most interested in. In the FutureLakes-Catalogue you can filter on column V (Goal of Mission) for schemes that address the three main aims: "Protect biodiversity", "Stop pollution" or "Enhance blue economy". Other useful filters may be Column F (filter on "Collaborative" or "Contributory" projects); Column Z (Scale of Operation: suggest to initially select "Europe" or "Global" for existing schemes that you could adopt, but also "National" together with Column W "Country of Origin").

Best practices

Below, we have selected some interesting examples of relevant citizen science schemes for lake communities documented in the database. Altogether, six schemes are presented, two for each Mission Ocean pillar (zero pollution, biodiversity, and blue economy). Each scheme is presented in a box, providing relevant details for the Demo Sites related to its practical implementation, including a general description, key aspects for engagement procedures, protocols, resource needs, data related procedures and barriers for upscaling.

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2.4.1 Zero Pollution

To explore potential schemes related to the Mission aim to reduce pollution, go to the [FutureLakes-Catalogue](#) and filter column V (Goal of Mission) for schemes that include “Stop pollution”.

Pollution monitoring using simple test kits

Freshwater Watch

FreshWater Watch (FWW) is a global project run by Earthwatch Europe, an environmental charity to investigate the health of global freshwater ecosystems. The aim is to connect people with freshwater ecosystems, growing their awareness and understanding, and motivating action to improve waterbody health. The scheme focuses on water quality monitoring and specifically on nitrate, phosphate, and turbidity measurements. Measurements are not precise concentrations but concentration ranges based on matching the test kit colour change to a colour chart. For example, nitrate concentrations are recorded in seven possible ranges, from less than detection limit (<0.2 NO₃-N mg/L) to above detection limit (>10 mg/L). Phosphate concentrations are recorded in seven possible ranges, from less than detection limit (<0.02 PO₄- P mg/L) to above detection limit (>1.0 mg/L). The data can be useful for campaigns to identify pollution hotspots in a lake catchment, but given the test kit ranges, they are less useful for monitoring changes in water quality in a Demo lake, as concentrations in most European lakes typically span only the lower two or three class ranges.

Engagement related aspects

FWW is categorised as a collaborative type of CS project, meaning that volunteers do not just contribute to data, but they are able to analyse data, disseminate finding and even modify the project design. It has a profile of a *mass participation census project* for the general public and the degree of the volunteers’ involvement (data collection, arrangement of data and analysis) is considered as *distributed intelligence*. Social networking can be done through the online platform and social media.

Protocols & Complexity

It runs in both mobile app and a web app. The mobile app, with interface translated in 42 languages, named “survey 123”, can be used for surveys, spotting, and image classification. The web-app has multiple functionalities like presenting ongoing CS projects and activities, good examples and lessons learned, displaying CS data and accompanying while offering guidelines, tools and significant scientific outcomes for people interested in participating (or involved) in CS activities. Volunteers’ training (for the water quality test kit) along with expert validation are necessary. Monthly monitoring is the optimum timescale proposed by FWW meaning a regular frequency is desired.

Investment in Cost & Time

It doesn’t require a constant internet connection as observations and water quality data can be uploaded after the monitoring routine, which includes the use of a water quality test kit, records and observations. Typically the community must purchase test kits for on-going monitoring campaigns (Demo sites should purchase for use during any FutureLakes campaign). Test kits cost about 70€ for quarterly sampling and €140 for monthly sampling campaigns¹.

Openness & Accessibility of CS generated data (robustness & policy uptake)

The CS platform can be found in SciStarter and it is a citizen science platform for specific projects. As the main scientific domain is water quality, it addresses SDG 6 (particularly 6.3 & 6.6) while there are more than 50,000 records with open access data availability. Its main policy aim is to support

¹ <https://www.freshwaterwatch.org/pages/individuals>

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policy decisions and management strategies that benefit both the ecosystem and communities (supporting WFD)

Scaling up – Barriers

The platform is still active, with the first records starting in 2012 on various water bodies (lakes, ponds, rivers, reservoirs). Although its origin is England- Wales, it works across Europe gaining a large social uptake. Stakeholders benefiting from this CS scheme are the volunteers themselves, Local Communities, Government Agencies, Research Organizations and various Environmental groups including sports fishing clubs and conservation-related organizations

For more information: www.freshwaterwatch.org

The Deltares Aquality App

Aquality, previously known as the Nitrate App, is an application developed by Deltares. It enables citizen scientists to measure, map, and share water quality parameters, including salinity and nutrient levels such as nitrate, ammonium, and phosphate, as well as nitrogen levels in soil. The project aims to involve farmers in collecting nitrate measurements to establish the relationship between various agricultural practices and water quality. The scheme focuses on water quality monitoring using test kits. Measurements are not precise concentrations but, similar to FWW, report concentration ranges based on matching the test kit colour change to a colour chart. The data can be useful for campaigns to identify pollution hotspots in a lake catchment, but given the test kit ranges, they are less useful for monitoring changes in water quality in a Demo lake, as concentrations in most European lakes typically span only the lower two or three class ranges.

Engagement-related aspects:

This project is an interest-group investigation aimed at engaging citizens who have prior knowledge, expertise, or interest in water quality issues. It specifically targets professionals in the field, such as farmers, scientists, water authorities, and water companies, who are concerned about nutrient losses and local water quality. The project operates as a contributory initiative with distributed intelligence. It was designed by scientists and encourages participants to contribute data on nitrate levels, salinity, soil nitrogen (N_{min}), ammonium, and phosphate measurements that can be visualized, edited and validated for better understanding. A social networking approach is employed through data sharing via the Deltares website and various social media platforms.

Protocols & Complexity:

The project operates through a mobile app called Aquality, which is available in six languages: English, Danish, Dutch, French, Greek, and Spanish. It assists volunteers by providing a simplified approach to conducting surveys, spotting, and classifying images and videos. Training is provided to help users learn how to utilise the test kits and the app effectively to submit their results. All data collected must be validated by experts. There are no specific time constraints regarding how often the app can be used; volunteers can utilize the Aquality app as frequently as needed, depending on their individual requirements and the specific goals of their monitoring efforts.

Investment in Cost & Time:

If an Internet connection is unavailable, the data will be prepared and automatically sent once the phone connects to Wi-Fi. After reaching the server, the measurements can be verified, visualized, edited, and more. The process requires water quality-related records based on the recommended approach, which includes water samples and test kits. Typically the community must purchase test

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kits for on-going monitoring campaigns (Demo sites should purchase for use during any FutureLakes campaign). Reporting is conducted using the volunteers' mobile phones.

Openness & Accessibility of data (robustness & policy uptake):

The CS platform hosting the Aquality app, developed by Deltares, is the GroundTruth, which, in this case, works as a citizen science platform for specific scientific topics. The primary fields of study are Water Science and Agriculture and Fisheries, as it monitors water quality for both irrigation and drinking purposes. The app and platform feature an open-access dataset containing over 500 records of measurements, which can be visualized directly using a web-based viewer. Additionally, there is a registered data viewer that provides access to private measurements not included in the public database. The platform addresses the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 1, 2, 6, 12, and 14, with a policy aim of supporting sustainable farming practices and protecting water resources by relevant EU directives.

Scaling up – Barriers

This initiative is designed for global water quality monitoring, to reduce water pollution and promote the blue economy, particularly in agricultural activities. It focuses on all types of freshwater suitable for irrigation and drinking purposes. Since its launch in 2016, it has gained substantial social support and continues to operate effectively. The project engages various stakeholders, including farmers, water authorities and companies, soil and groundwater quality specialists, as well as institutions and researchers.

For more information: www.deltares.nl/en/software-and-data/products/aquality-app

Pollution monitoring using a high quality laboratory - *Big Windermere Survey*

Given the limitations of using test kits, an alternative approach is to involve an accredited laboratory in the CitSci campaign. This could be a laboratory in a university department, research organisation or a public authority. One successful example of this is the *Big Windermere Survey*. This was a collaboration between members of the local community and professional scientists at Lancaster University and the Freshwater Biological Association (FBA). It aimed to provide robust scientific data collected from over 100 locations around Windermere's shoreline and the catchment to understand spatial and seasonal changes in water quality and identify pollution hotspots. 350 citizen scientists collected over 1,000 samples of water from the lake and its wider catchment, during 10 sampling events spread across 2.5 years. The water samples were analysed for 15 key water quality parameters, including concentrations of phosphorus and the bacteria *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) and Intestinal Enterococci (IE), critical indicators of ecosystem health and of the quality of water for lake users.

Engagement related aspects

The Big Windermere Survey is categorised as a contributory project, as volunteers largely just contribute to data collection. It has a profile of a *mass participation census project* for the public and the degree of the volunteers' involvement (data collection) is considered as *distributed intelligence*. Social networking is done through social media.

Protocols & Complexity

The survey involved training of volunteers in sample collection using water sampling kits funded by the project's sponsors. An online training video was also provided. The samples are deposited by the citizen scientists at several drop-off points around the catchment and are then transported to the laboratory that day. The programme undertook quarterly monitoring and continued for 2.5

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years. A range of communication events and products communicated the results of the activity to the participants and more widely through the media and the project website.

Investment in Cost & Time

Participants invest their time and fuel costs to reach sampling locations and drop off samples. The cost of the sample analyses and communications were covered by the project's sponsors. There was also a large investment of scientists' volunteer time involved.

Openness & Accessibility of CS generated data (robustness & policy uptake)

The results can be downloaded from the project website and summary reports and web storyboards summarise the results in accessible language. The results provide high quality evidence to support WFD investigative monitoring across catchments and provide widescale assessment of water quality around lake shorelines, supporting water users in their knowledge needs.

Scaling up – Barriers

This initiative is designed for annual or seasonal water quality campaigns to provide a very comprehensive picture of water quality around a whole lake catchment. It is particularly useful for large complex catchments or lakes with multiple bathing sites. It could be applied to any lake where samples could be readily transported to a high-quality laboratory. It requires relatively large funding for sample analysis and scientist time in running the sampling campaigns and communicating the results. This funding could be sought externally (public or private financing), through crowd funding or through the FutureLakes Demo site budgets and staff time. The project engages various stakeholders, including farmers, water authorities and companies, soil and groundwater quality specialists, as well as institutions and researchers.

For more information: <https://www.fba.org.uk/volunteer/the-big-windermere-survey>

Also see some other relevant initiatives like:

Name of CS Initiative	Project Website Link
CitClops- EyeOnWater	http://www.citclops.eu/
Ecomore	https://ecomore.inoe.ro/
Secchi Dip-in	www.nalms.org/secchidipin/
The Big Microplastic Survey	https://microplasticsurvey.org/

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2.4.2 Biodiversity

To explore potential schemes related to the Mission aim to “Protect and Restore Biodiversity”, go to the [FutureLakes-Catalogue](#) and filter column V (Goal of Mission) for schemes that include “Protect biodiversity”.

BioBlitz event (using iNaturalist)

A BioBlitz is a short-term event (usually 24 hours) in which teams of volunteers (families, students, teachers, and other community members) work together with experts to find and identify as many species of plants, animals, fungi, and other organisms as possible in a specific defined area. Experienced scientists and expert naturalists typically lead different specialist activities which community members can join to learn how to survey and identify species (e.g. electro-fishing, aquatic plant survey, bird count, benthic invertebrates, mammal camera traps, bat surveys, etc.). For FutureLakes this would most likely focus on freshwater biodiversity in the lake, but could also include a defined area of land around your lake (such as a nature reserve boundary) or inflow and outflow streams.

The aim is for a fun, learning activity and challenges can be set to find or discover many species as possible and particularly to look for any rare species known for the area. Ideally, standard survey methods should be used and a quantified search effort (e.g. 2 kick samples at 3 locations, 10 plant transects) to allow repeat surveys for any groups in future years. For some groups, such as benthic invertebrates, invasive species, or amphibians, standard citizen science schemes are available to use during a BioBlitz. Several of these are listed in the [FutureLakes-Catalogue](#) (filter column L: “Mobile App” or “Both”).

All species identified in the BioBlitz should be recorded and participants should be shown how to upload records to local or national databases that manage biodiversity records. To help with this, several useful biological recording apps are available to use. Some are country-specific (e.g. Artsorakelet in Norway which also helps with identification), but the **iNaturalist app** is probably the most widely used in Europe. Further details of iNaturalist are described in the catalogue (Scheme #71) and are summarised below:

iNaturalist is an online social network of people sharing biodiversity information to help each other learn about nature. Its objective is to connect people to nature and advance biodiversity science and conservation.

Engagement related aspects

iNaturalist is classified as a contributory scheme designed by scientists, meaning volunteers only contribute with data, as well as a mass-participation census project aiming to involve the general public in biodiversity monitoring. The involvement of volunteers is just crowdsourcing of monitoring records. The iNaturalist uses multiple ways for citizen engagement and the app encourages community interaction, allowing users to follow each other, participate in projects, and share their observations with a global network of scientists and naturalists.

Protocols & Complexity

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It runs in a mobile app with interface translated into 35 languages, and is operational for surveys, spotting, image & video classification and gamification. No previous training is needed by the volunteers, but expert validation is foreseen for proper taxonomy. Monitoring doesn't have any timescale restrictions as it can be used all year long but demands regular frequency in records.

Investment in Cost & Time Vs Benefits

iNaturalist has both a mobile app and a web app, hosting biodiversity (species) observations. There is no need for a constant internet connection as records can be uploaded later. The recording procedure is not demanding, as simple observations (photos) of species are enough to contribute to biodiversity monitoring using just a mobile phone as a measurement and reporting device.

Openness & Accessibility of CS generated data (robustness & policy uptake)

This CS scheme focuses on Natural Science addressing various SDGs (2, 3, 4, 13, 15, 17), primarily focused on promoting responsible data sharing, community engagement, and protecting user privacy and data. The type of platform is a typical citizen science platform for specific projects and can also be found in SciStarter, while the platform also hosts other contributory projects (like Cyanoscope). The data are openly accessible and are suitable for policy uptake (e.g. monitoring status and trends of species for the Habitats Directive & Nature Restoration Regulation).

Scaling up – Barriers

Despite its origin in the USA (California), it operates on a global scale and can be applied to all types of freshwater and terrestrial habitats. The platform is active, providing data, having large social uptake addressing multiple stakeholders like the iNaturalist Community, Donors, Partner Organizations, Scientists and Conservationists. More than 200 million records have been collected since 2008 when it started operating. Besides biodiversity protection, it could also produce useful tool for eco-tourism to support the Mission Ocean & Waters pillar on enhancing the blue economy.

For more information: <https://www.bnhc.org.uk/run-your-own-bioblitz> and <https://www.inaturalist.org/>

AmphiBiom

The AmphiBiom project is an example of a CitSci project targeting specific biodiversity protection. It is dedicated to recording and creating (new) habitats for frogs, toads and other amphibians. The main aim is to show all participants that they themselves can promote the survival of this highly threatened group with just a little effort and to strengthen the general freshwater literacy that is needed to better understand species and habitat protection measures.

Engagement related aspects:

It is a *mass-participation census project* aiming to involve the general public, not requiring prior knowledge or expertise. It is a plain Contributory project, which means it was designed by scientists and for which the involved parties contribute data. This means the involvement of volunteers is just crowdsourcing of monitoring records. Social networking approaches happen via the AmphiBiom blog.

Protocols & Complexity:

It runs on both mobile app (AmphiApp) and a web app (Österreich forscht). The mobile app which works in English and German, assists volunteers to perform spotting, sensing along with Image and

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video classification. This happens through a gamified procedure. The webpage presents the CS campaigns and activities, organises and displays collected data and information, provides guidelines and tools for CS activities, promotes good examples and lessons learned while offers outcomes and suggestion to those willing to engage with citizen science. It does not require volunteer training, but records are screened by experts. It runs all year long and allows for regular monitoring frequency.

Investment in Cost & Time:

It requires an internet connection to run the app and upload amphibian footage. What it needs is simple observation records with no additional measurement or reporting device other than the volunteers' mobile phone.

Openness & Accessibility of data (robustness & policy uptake):

The CS platform is a national one targeting Natural Science as a primary field of science. Through the structured website one can access (open access) more than 1000 records of amphibians. It addresses a range of biodiversity related SDGs (SDG 6, SDG 13, SDG 15 (15.5 & 15.8)). Its policy aims are the EU Habitats Directive and the European Biodiversity Strategy 2020.

Scaling up – Barriers

Developed by Boku University and designed for biodiversity monitoring, at a national scale, it targeted lakes, ponds, garden ponds, puddles etc. where one could find toads located in Austria. It has the potential for upscaling, as it has operated since 2023 and is still ongoing. It further targets as stakeholders all biodiversity and particularly amphibian enthusiasts reaching up to Environmental NGOs, Local Authorities and academia.

For more information: www.amphi.at

Also check other interesting initiatives:

Name of CS Initiative	Project Website Link
Invasive Alien Species in Europe	https://easin.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ias
National Lake Blitz	https://livinglakescanada.ca/project/national-lake-blitz/
New Hampshire Dragonfly Survey	https://nhaudubon.org/new-hampshire-dragonfly-survey/
Tauchen für Naturschutz (Diving for Nature Conservation)	https://ec-jrc.github.io/citsci-explorer/project/10387.html

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2.4.3 Blue Economy

There are no existing CitSci schemes explicitly focused on monitoring the blue economy. In FutureLakes, we may want to consider designing a bespoke scheme for communities to record water use and income generated through businesses associated with recreational activities and eco-tourism. To explore potential schemes that could collect useful data, go to the [FutureLakes-Catalogue](#) and filter column V (Goal of Mission) for schemes that include “Enhance blue economy”.

MyCatch

MyCatch is a mobile app developed by Angler’s Atlas, which has been a proven, invaluable online resource for anglers since 1999. Angler’s Atlas began collecting angler data for science in the early 2000s, and it is evident that MyCatch has facilitated the efficient collection of more meaningful and practical data. In particular, the app allows citizen scientists to contribute data directly to fisheries, biologists, and researchers. The project aims to develop more accurate stock assessments using both traditional research methods and fishing logs.

Engagement-related aspects:

This project is a place-based community action scheme targeting local communities, and it is defined as a crowdsourcing contributory project, meaning it was originally designed by scientists and for which members of the public primarily contribute data. The project is recognized as a leader in app-based events, enabling users (the general public) to organize and customize events, adding an interesting and playful dimension to social engagement.

Protocols & Complexity:

The project operates through a mobile app called MyCatch, which is currently available only in English. This app helps volunteers record their fishing catches, participate in fishing events, and track their statistics. No training is required, as the app is designed to be user-friendly and straightforward, primarily targeting volunteers who are already familiar with fishing. All data collected through the app are analysed by researchers and biologists who are interested in fish conservation. There are no specific time constraints on how often the app can be used; volunteers can use the MyCatch app as frequently as they need, based on their individual requirements and the specific goals of their monitoring efforts.

Investment in Cost & Time:

The MyCatch app does not require a constant internet connection. It stores fishing trip data offline and uploads it when a connection is available. This allows users to log their fishing trips even in areas with limited or no cellular service. The monitoring process requires recording fish by catching them, taking a photo, and instantly releasing them (Catch-Photo-Release). This whole procedure is part of the event. Reporting is conducted using volunteers’ mobile phones.

Openness & Accessibility of data (robustness & policy uptake):

The CS platform hosting the MyCatch app, developed by Angler’s Atlas, is the SciStarter, which in this case works as a citizen science platform for specific projects. The primary fields of study are Natural Science and Agriculture and Fisheries, as it monitors fish species for both recreational and market purposes. The app and platform contain more than 13000 fish records, but they do not provide completely open access data. While anglers can access their own data within the app, and researchers can access aggregated and anonymized data for fisheries research, the app explicitly protects the privacy of anglers’ “secret spots” and does not release point data to the public. The platform addresses the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 2, 6 and 14, with a policy aim to help inform fisheries management and conservation.

Scaling up – Barriers

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This initiative is designed for regional monitoring to enhance the blue economy, particularly in fishing activities. It focuses on all types of water bodies suitable for fishing (freshwater and marine). Since its launch in 2018, it has gained large social support and continues to operate effectively. The project engages various stakeholders, including Fisheries Managers, Scientists, Recreational Fishers, Advisory Groups, State and Regional Agencies, and the General public.

For more information: <https://mycatch.ca/>

Bloomin' Algae

Bloomin' Algae (<https://www.ceh.ac.uk/our-science/projects/bloomin-algae>) is a citizen science app developed by the UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology to enable the presence of blue-green algae, or cyanobacteria, to be reported by the public when they are observed on freshwaters (predominantly lakes and reservoirs). Users submit photos of potential Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) and an expert verifier is notified and checks these to confirm if it looks like a cyanobacterial bloom. Local authorities, public agencies, businesses and water supply companies can also set up notifications to be informed when a bloom is reported or verified in their region to support their risk management. The App supports public health risk management of HABs as it helps speed up the delivery of warnings to the public about water use and directly educates people to recognise and understand better the risks to themselves, their children and animals.

As well as recording the location and date of the bloom, users have to submit a photograph of the bloom so that records can be verified. Optionally, they are asked to describe any water-related activities taking place in the area when the image was taken. Such activities include angling, swimming, watersports and dog walking. This additional information allows the potential risk to be assessed to other water users or animals and can inform the speed of response needed.

The app provides data on seasonality and frequency of bloom incidents as well as information of the coverage of blooms along a lake shoreline. It only provides qualitative information on the magnitude of the bloom, although if a surface accumulation is present, this is often enough evidence to register it as very high cell densities to be classified as a high risk event for water use. The data cannot be used alone for WFD assessment of bloom frequency and magnitude but does provide a source of information to combine with satellite measures of chlorophyll-a that could be used quantitatively and be developed as a WFD metric for bloom frequency and magnitude. It is also proposed to be used as an Essential Biodiversity Variable (EBV) for freshwaters to measure ecosystem quality².

The Bloomin' Algae App is now available to use in Europe in Belgium, Netherlands, Luxembourg, Norway, Ireland and the UK and is available to use in several languages (English, French, Dutch, Norwegian and Spanish). It can be extended to other European countries. The App has been translated into several languages (English, Spanish, French, Dutch, Norwegian, Swahili, Mapudungun). A new version of the App is being developed to record outbreaks of water hyacinth and other nuisance aquatic weeds.

Engagement-related aspects:

This project is a multi-national scheme that targets local communities. It was originally designed by scientists in collaboration with environmental and public health agencies in Scotland. The data are contributed, primarily, by members of the public using the Bloomin' Algae App on their mobile

² <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2351989425003002>

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phones. The App is presented to people at public engagement events that are usually lake-specific. In some countries, such as Scotland, Northern Ireland and Luxembourg, annual campaigns using national and local media (TV, newspaper and radio) are carried out at the start of summer to re-engage the public for the main bloom season. Regulatory agencies in many countries rely on data from the App for high frequency and widescale monitoring of algal blooms to act quickly to mitigate their impacts on public and animal health. A video has also been produced that provides an engaging overview of the App and its capabilities. (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-kfKxBSL2Ks>).

Protocols & Complexity:

The Bloomin' Algae App focuses recording on cyanobacteria at a macro-level - i.e. the visual appearance of scums, which constitute a high risk to public and animal health. It provides a pictorial guide to help users differentiate between potentially toxic cyanobacteria and other floating scums and plant material.

When records are submitted, they are checked by a local verifier who classifies the submission as correct, plausible or incorrect before they are added to a live map that displays current and historical records (Figure 1). Length of record varies by country, with data having been collected from the UK since 2017.

Figure 1 Bloomin' Algae records submitted in Europe between January 2024 and September 2025

Investment in Cost & Time:

Although the App is free to use at no cost, there are underlying costs of maintaining the App and upgrading the software; these amount to about Euros 1,500 per year currently covered by UKCEH or partner organisations. In addition, there is a cost of about Euros 1,000 associated with adding extra countries to the system, and translation costs if required. There are also costs incurred by verifiers; these amount

to about 5 mins per record (approximately 85 h per year per 1000 records). From a user perspective, submitting a record takes 5 minutes and requires access to a mobile phone signal.

The app is easy to use and intuitive, so little or no training is required. However, awareness raising sessions to remind the public to use the app are often needed and feedback is often provided to encourage widespread and continuous use and further checks that users can make visually.

Openness & Accessibility of data (robustness & policy uptake):

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The data submitted are stored in UKCEH’s iRecord data centre (<https://irecord.org.uk>), which is maintained by the Biological Records Centre (<https://www.brc.ac.uk/>). Data are available to view and download from <https://bloominalgae.ceh.ac.uk> and also on partner websites in Norway, Luxembourg, etc.

Scaling up – Barriers

The main barriers to scaling up from individual country level to global scale are securing the funding required to add additional countries and associated translation. Raising and maintaining the profile of the App with the general public/citizen science user community also requires sustained effort over time, e.g. thorough the provision of regular newsletters and updates. The biggest barrier to scaling up is commitment of one or more trained verifiers per country; this currently depends on volunteers although it is run in some countries (e.g. Scotland, Northern Ireland, Luxembourg) by agency staff with the time involved included in their job.

For more information: <https://www.ceh.ac.uk/our-science/projects/bloomin-algae>

Also see some other interesting initiatives like:

Name of CS Initiative	Project Website Link
Crowdwater	https://crowdwater.ch/en/welcome-to-crowdwater/
INTCATCH	https://intcatch.eu/index.php/citizen-science
Chronolog Environmental Monitoring	www.chronolog.io/project/IDN
Järvi-wiki	A web based service for cyanobacteria observations in lakes (and sea). Used both as a tracking tool as well as a citizen involvement platform https://www.jarviwiki.fi/

2.4.4 Multiple Pillars

Catchment Based Approach

The Catchment Based Approach (CaBA) is an inclusive, civil society-led initiative that works in partnership with Government, Local Authorities, Water Companies, businesses and more, in order to maximize the natural value of our environment. It was designed to leverage the public's participation in data collection and monitoring and foster community involvement in finding solutions to protect freshwater environments. It covers Pollution, Biodiversity and Blue Economy.

Engagement related aspects:

It is a place-based community action scheme targeting local communities and set as a collaborative project, meaning it was originally designed by scientists, but volunteers, besides just collecting data, help to refine project design, analyze data through “distributed intelligence”. Social networking approaches include Collaborative partnerships, Communication and Information Sharing.

Protocols & Complexity:

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It is based on a web-app with full functionality, meaning it presents active citizen science projects and activities while displays CS data and information and besides that it provides overall guidelines and tools that can be used to support CS activities in general. It further highlights good practice examples and lessons learned, offering relevant scientific outcomes for those interested. It is quite demanding as it asks for volunteer training and expert validation as it demands regular all year long monitoring of parameters.

Investment in Cost & Time Vs Benefits

It does not require constant internet connection as it operates through platforms and Hubs that provide site-specific water management solutions. In particular, the CaBA utilizes various measurements to assess and improve water environments, such as water quality parameters, flow rates, habitat assessments, land use patterns, measures of public awareness and participation in catchment management. Reporting is conducted using the provided Web app.

Openness & Accessibility of CS generated data (robustness & policy uptake):

Though the structured website many kinds of data can be accessed as more than 100 layers of information are stored there. The platform is a blend of CS and national one, hosting data spanning among Social, Natural, Water Sciences, Agriculture and Fisheries and hence addresses a large range of SDGs meaning 2, 6, 8, 13 and 15. Its major policy aim is the Water Framework Directive

Scaling up – Barriers

As it was designed to monitor different types of Rivers, lakes and coastal waters in a national (England) scale of operation. It allows to upscale as it operates since 2013 and is still ongoing. It further targets as stakeholders a series of actors spanning from Landowners, Angling Clubs and Farmer Representative Bodies up to Environmental NGOs, Water Companies, Local Authorities & Government Agencies including also Academia and Businesses having a large social uptake

For more information: <https://catchmentbasedapproach.org/learn/citizen-science-volunteer-monitoring/>

EcoServ

The EcoServ project is a participatory research initiative focused on enhancing ecosystem services in Armenia, particularly within the Hrazdan River basin and Lake Sevan. It employs a transdisciplinary and citizen science approach, engaging a wide range of stakeholders including researchers, educators, students, local communities, and businesses. The project aims to improve the management of aquatic ecosystems by assessing and understanding ecosystem services and building capacity for sustainable practices.

Engagement related aspects:

It is a place-based community action scheme targeting local communities, with special emphasis placed on supporting women’s sustainable businesses. It is a contributory project, which means it was designed by scientists to develop an ecosystem services assessment framework, while volunteers only contribute their experiences (qualitative data) and monitoring data (quantitative data) through “crowd sourcing”. Social networking approaches include social media campaigns, workshops, events (EcoServ summer school), and networking platforms for social entrepreneurs.

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Protocols & Complexity:

The project does not provide a web or mobile app, but its complexity and requirements for protocols depend on the type of solution. Mainly, the CS provides capacity-building activities and training programs to empower participants. It focuses on local schools providing teaching material and tools (bioindication methods) in ecosystem services assessment. The complexity basically lies in the willingness to participate, and protocols are inevitable since the main concept of the CS is to provide a framework, which involves rules and guidelines.

Investment in Cost & Time Vs Benefits

It does not require a constant internet connection as it operates through direct communication and cooperation. The EcoServ project utilizes various approaches to assess water resources management, business training programs, summer schools, specific-oriented master classes, teaching practices, field campaigns using bioindication methods by collecting water samples and making observations etc. Reporting is conducted through publications and the project’s official website.

Openness & Accessibility of CS generated data (robustness & policy uptake):

Though the structured website many kinds of data can be accessed as more than 100 layers of information are stored there. The platform is a blend of CS and national one, hosting data spanning among Social, Natural, Water Sciences, Agriculture and Fisheries and hence addresses a large range of SDGs meaning 2, 6, 8, 13 and 15. Its major policy aim is the Water Framework Directive.

This CS doesn’t provide a repository with open-access data, but it presents keys findings and conclusions through international conferences, reports and publications. The scheme focuses on Water Science and directly contributes to achieving SDG 4 (Quality Education), SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation), and SDG 15 (Life on Land). Its policy aims are to improve aquatic ecosystem management in Armenia by assessing ecosystem services and developing an ecosystem services management module for university students.

Scaling up – Barriers

The project was designed to monitor the Hrazdan River basin and Lake Sevan in Armenia on a local scale. It launched in 2023 and will continue until 2027, with the potential for upscaling in the future. Initially, the social uptake may be limited due to the scale of operation, but there are promising opportunities as the initiative engages a diverse group of stakeholders, including researchers, educators, students, local community members, farmers, and industry professionals.

For more information: <https://ecoserv.boku.ac.at/>

Also see some other relevant initiatives like:

Name of CS Initiative	Project Website Link
GLOBE Observer	https://observer.globe.gov/about/citizen-science
MapNat	https://www.ufz.de/index.php?en=40618

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ProBleu	https://probleu.school/
The ninth phase of the Intergovernmental Hydrological Programme (IHP-IX Strategic Plan)	www.unesco.org/en/ihp/priority#:~:text=The%20ninth%20phase%20of%20the,Sustainable%20Development%20Goals%20(SDGs).

2.5 Readings recommendations

Further reading recommendations refer to the engagement practices selection, on guidelines for selecting and designing CS and on the future of CS in the EU:

- o <https://citizenscience.si/en/a-new-book-is-published-how-and-when-to-involve-crowds-in-scientific-research/>
- o https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/oecd-guidelines-for-citizen-participation-processes_f765caf6-en/full-report.html
- o <https://nora.nerc.ac.uk/id/eprint/510644/1/N510644CR.pdf>
- o <https://citizensciencefp10.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/PositionPaper.pdf>

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### M3. CS Catalogue

## Annex 1: The catalogue

All processed lake related CS Schemes are indexed and detailed here:

[FutureLakes\\_Catalogue\\_Final.xlsx](#)